

A Multidimensional Assessment of Compliance with Turkish Sustainability Reporting Standards in the Borsa Istanbul Transportation and Logistics Sector

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the compliance levels of companies operating in the Transportation and Logistics sector of the Istanbul Stock Exchange (BIST) with the Turkish Sustainable Reporting Standards (TSRS) for the year 2024, within a multidimensional and comparative framework. The publicly available annual reports of 10 out of 12 companies in the sector that were determined to have published sustainability compliance reports were examined using content analysis. TSRS compliance was structured under four main dimensions: Governance, Environmental, Social, and Stakeholder Engagement; each criterion was scored as 0 (no explanation), 1 (partial compliance), and 2 (full compliance). Criteria not directly related to the field of activity were excluded from the analysis, and a composite TSRS_{Total} index was created using measurement and dimension indices. Descriptive statistics, reliability analyses, correlation tests, Friedman tests, and hierarchical clustering analysis results obtained using SPSS software showed that the overall compliance level in the sector is moderate, with the environmental dimension exhibiting higher performance. Strong positive relationships between the dimensions indicate that sustainability practices are addressed holistically, while clustering analysis reveals different levels of sustainability maturity among firms. The study contributes to the quantitative and comparable measurement of TSRS compliance at the sectoral level.

Keywords: Sustainability Reporting, BIST, Sustainability Accounting, TSRS, Index Analysis

Introduction

Sustainability reporting is one of the corporate reporting areas that aims to produce comparable information for investors and other stakeholders by enabling companies to transparently disclose their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) impacts. It has gained momentum with the increasing role of ESG information in decision-making processes in capital markets and the requirement for companies to report climate/environmental risks along with financial impacts. In Turkey, with the publication of TSRS 1 and TSRS 2 and the Board Decision regarding the scope of TSRS application, a new reporting period has been initiated for accounting periods starting in 2024 and beyond.(KGK, 2024c, 2024a, 2024b).

The transportation and logistics sector is considered among the areas with a high level of "materiality" in the sustainability literature due to issues such as energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, supply chain impacts, and occupational health and safety. Recent studies focusing on identifying sustainability indicators specific to the logistics sector and analyzing the content of reports show that the sector can exhibit different reporting maturities in terms of environmental indicators (emissions/energy), social indicators (employee safety/labor practices), and governance indicators (policy, risk management, audit/verification) (Albuquerque et al., 2023; Jayarathna et al., 2022a).

In Turkey, disclosures regarding sustainability for publicly traded companies are not limited to voluntary reporting but are supported by regulatory frameworks. The Capital Markets Board's "Sustainability Principles Compliance Framework" adopts a "comply or disclose" approach, requiring companies to disclose their compliance with sustainability principles and the reasons for non-compliance in their annual reports. Borsa Istanbul contributes to the development of the reporting ecosystem through its sustainability-focused index and guideline initiatives. (Borsa İstanbul A.Ş., 2022, 2024; SPK, 2022).

This study examines the multidimensional compliance levels of companies operating in the Transportation and Logistics sector of the Istanbul Stock Exchange (BIST) that have published sustainability compliance reports for 2024. The companies included in the analysis are: Beyaz Filo, Çelebi Hava Servisi, GSD Denizcilik, Gür-Sel Turizm Taşımacılık, Pasifik Eurasia Lojistik, Pegasus Hava Taşımacılığı, Reysaş Taşımacılık ve Lojistik, Türk Hava Yolları (THY), Trabzon Liman İşletmeciliği, and Tureks Turizm Taşımacılık. These companies constitute a highly representative sample for comparative analysis of sustainability practices due to their diverse areas of activity within the sector (aviation, maritime transport, land logistics, port operations, and fleet leasing). (BEYAZ, 2024; CLEBI, 2024; GRSEL, 2024; GSDDE, 2024; PASEU, 2024; PGSUS, 2024; RYSAS, 2024; THYAO, 2024; TLMAN, 2024; TUREX, 2024).

The aim of this study is to measure the TSRS compliance levels of companies in the BIST Transportation & Logistics sector that have published sustainability compliance reports for 2024 in four main dimensions: Governance (A), Environmental (B), Social (C), and Stakeholder Engagement (D), and to statistically reveal similarities/differences within the sector. In the study, each criterion was rated as 0 (no explanation), 1 (partial compliance), and 2 (full compliance); furthermore, for criteria not directly related to the field of activity, the companies' "not applicable" statements were considered separately, and the denominator was adjusted in a way that would reduce measurement bias in the index calculations. Descriptive statistics, internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha), interdimensional relationships (correlation), and hierarchical clustering of company profiles were conducted on the obtained A_{Index} , B_{Index} , C_{Index} , D_{Index} , and composite $TSRS_{Total}$ index, and the sustainability compliance outlook of the sector was evaluated in a multidimensional way.

Materials And Methods

This study is based on cross-sectional and document analysis aimed at quantitatively measuring and comparatively analyzing the TSRS compliance levels of firms operating in the Transportation and Logistics sector of the Istanbul Stock Exchange (BIST) for the year 2024. The research population consists of transportation and logistics firms traded on BIST. As a result of the examination, it was determined that 10 out of 12 firms in the sector published a "Sustainability Compliance Report" or "Annual Statement" for 2024. The analyses were carried out only on the 10 firms that published the report.

Data Collection and Coding Process

The data source for the research consists of publicly available sustainability compliance reports and annual statements of companies for the year 2024. The reports were examined using the systematic document analysis method and analyzed using a coding scheme structured according to the criteria determined within the framework of TSRS. Each company report was examined separately, and after the coding process was completed, the data from all companies were combined into a single dataset and transferred to the SPSS environment in order to perform comparative analysis. In the coding process, each criterion was scored with a three-point rating system:

- 0 = No
- 1 = Partially
- 2 = Yes

However, it has been observed that some criteria are declared as "irrelevant" by companies when they are not directly related to their field of activity. Such statements have not been methodologically considered equivalent to the "not applied" category. Criteria marked as "not relevant" have been systematically left blank and not included in the index calculations. This prevents companies from artificially receiving low scores due to criteria outside their scope of activity. A pairwise approach was preferred for missing data in the analyses.

Defining Dimensions and Index Creation Approach

Four main dimensions have been created to measure the level of TSRS compliance:

- (A) Governance
- (B) Environmental
- (C) Social
- (D) Stakeholder Engagement

When raw coding scores (0–1–2) are analyzed directly, it becomes difficult to make comparisons between firms due to the different number of criteria in each dimension. Therefore, dimension-based normalized average scores have been calculated (Beyazyol & Ataman, 2023; Ok & Göktaş, 2024).

The dimension index was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Index}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{k_j} X_{ij}}{k_j}$$

Where:

X_{ij} denotes the score obtained by firm j on criterion i ; k_j : represents the number of applicable criteria (i.e., criteria relevant to the firm's operational scope) for firm j .

In this approach, the denominator was not kept fixed; only the applicable criteria were considered for each firm. This minimized measurement bias that might arise from differences in areas of activity. In addition to dimension-based analyses, a composite TSRS_{Total} index was created to express the overall sustainability compliance level of firms with a single indicator (Velte, 2017). This index was calculated by taking the equally weighted arithmetic mean of the averages of four dimensions:

$$\text{TSRS}_{\text{Total}} = \frac{A_{\text{Index}} + B_{\text{Index}} + C_{\text{Index}} + D_{\text{Index}}}{4}$$

The equal weighting approach was preferred because the TSRS framework does not define a normative priority ranking among the dimensions. Thus, no dimension was given artificial superiority. With this index structure:

- Comparisons between dimensions could be made,
- The overall sustainability profile could be measured,
- Correlation and clustering analyses could be applied.

Reliability Analysis

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was calculated to evaluate the internal consistency of the created dimension indices. Cronbach's Alpha is a commonly used statistical indicator to assess internal consistency between items and the reliability of the scale in multi-item measurements. The coefficient is calculated using the following formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum s_i^2}{s_T^2} \right)$$

In this formula, k denotes the number of items constituting the scale, s_i^2 represents the variance of each individual item, and s_T^2 refers to the variance of the total score. As reflected in the formulation, Cronbach's Alpha is based on the proportion of total variance attributable to the covariance among items, thereby assessing the internal consistency and homogeneity of the scale. As the degree of inter-item consistency increases, the Alpha coefficient approaches 1, indicating a higher level of reliability (Taber, 2018).

According to generally accepted threshold values in the literature, Alpha values of 0.70 and above indicate an acceptable level of reliability, values of 0.80 and above indicate high reliability, and values of 0.90 and above indicate very high internal consistency. The Alpha values calculated in this study are above these thresholds, demonstrating that the created TSRS dimension indices offer a reliable and internally consistent measurement structure. (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were calculated to reveal the sectoral distribution of firms' TSRS compliance levels. In this context, mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values were determined for the A_{Index} , B_{Index} , C_{Index} , D_{Index} , and composite $TSRS_{Total}$ index variables. Mean values represent the overall compliance level of firms in the relevant dimension; standard deviation indicates the degree of distribution and variability among firms. Minimum and maximum values reveal the lowest and highest performance levels within the sector, providing information about the presence of outliers. The main purpose of calculating descriptive statistics is to reveal the general overview of the sector's sustainability compliance profile and to determine the level of heterogeneity among firms. In particular, standard deviation values allow for the evaluation of whether compliance levels within the sector are homogeneous or dispersed. A low standard deviation indicates that firms show similar levels of compliance; a high standard deviation indicates significant differences among firms. This analysis also serves as a preliminary assessment for subsequent statistical tests. Comparing mean values across dimensions forms the basis for difference analysis using the Friedman test; Examining distribution characteristics facilitates the interpretation of correlation and clustering analyses. Thus, descriptive statistics are used not only as descriptive tools but also as a guiding step in the analytical process.

Correlation Analysis

The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the direction and strength of the linear relationship between the TSRS dimensions. The Pearson correlation coefficient is a parametric statistic that measures the degree of linear relationship between two continuous variables and is calculated using the following formula (Pearson, 1931):

$$r = \frac{\sum(X - \bar{X})(Y - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum(X - \bar{X})^2 \sum(Y - \bar{Y})^2}}$$

X and Y are two related variables, \bar{X} and \bar{Y} represent the means of these variables. The coefficient takes values between -1 and $+1$, indicating a strong positive relationship as it approaches $+1$, a strong negative relationship as it approaches -1 , and no relationship as it approaches 0 . (Akoglu, 2018).

Pearson correlation analysis was preferred because the dimension indices were calculated on a continuous scale using mean scores. Although the basic coding is ordinal, the calculation of dimension-based mean scores transformed the variables into approximately continuous scales, allowing for the application of parametric correlation analysis. Considering the small sample size ($n=10$), a two-way significance test was used, and the significance level was set at 0.05 . (Norman, 2010; Schober et al., 2018).

Correlation analysis was first used to test whether the A_{Index} , B_{Index} , C_{Index} , and D_{Index} dimensions interacted with each other. This allowed for an assessment of whether sustainability practices

were implemented in a fragmented or holistic manner. High and positive correlations between the dimensions indicate that companies are implementing sustainability practices within an integrated structure. Conversely, low correlation values indicate divergence between the dimensions. Furthermore, by examining the correlation coefficients between the TSRS_Total index and each sub-dimension, the analysis revealed which dimensions more strongly represented the overall sustainability score. This approach provides an opportunity to evaluate the structural consistency of the composite index and the contribution levels of the dimensions. Thus, correlation analysis not only identified the relationship but also served as an analytical tool revealing the internal dynamics of the index structure.

Friedman Test

The Friedman test was applied to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between the TSRS dimension means. Due to the limited sample size (n=10) and the inability to reliably test whether the data structure met the assumption of normal distribution, the non-parametric Friedman test was preferred instead of the parametric Repeated Measures ANOVA. The Friedman test is a rank-based method used to compare the medians of three or more related measurements belonging to the same sample group and provides reliable results, especially in small samples. (Conover, 1999; Gibbons & Chakraborti, 2025).

Since each firm is evaluated across four different dimensions (A, B, C, and D), the measurements have a dependent (related) structure. The Friedman test ranks the dimension scores for each firm internally and compares the rank means of the dimensions, thus offering a comparison independent of distribution assumptions.(Friedman, 1937).

The Friedman test statistic is calculated as follows:

$$x^2 = \frac{12}{nk(k+1)} \sum R_j^2 - 3n(k+1)$$

Where:

- n: number of firms
- k: number of dimensions compared
- R_j: rank sum for each dimension

The calculated test statistic approximately follows a chi-square distribution and is evaluated with k-1 degrees of freedom. A statistically significant difference between dimensions is considered to exist if the obtained p-value is less than 0.05. This analysis evaluated whether sustainability practices are concentrated in a particular dimension or whether there is a systematic priority difference among the dimensions. If the test result is significant, it is concluded that firms show higher compliance in certain TSRS dimensions compared to others; if it is not significant, it is concluded that sustainability practices exhibit a balanced distribution among the dimensions. Therefore, the Friedman test was used in this study not only for difference analysis but also to reveal whether sustainability practices are holistic or dimension-focused.

Clustering Analysis

Hierarchical clustering analysis was applied to evaluate the sustainability performance of firms not only based on average scores but also within the framework of multidimensional profile structures. This analysis aims to reveal the typology of sustainability profiles in the sector by grouping firms with similar TSRS compliance levels under the same groups. Thus, it was determined whether firms are homogeneous or positioned under different sustainability clusters. Due to the limited sample size (n=10), the hierarchical clustering method, which is not sensitive to the number of observations, was preferred instead of parametric classification methods. The Ward method was used as the linkage method in the analysis. The Ward method performs the inter-cluster merging process at each step in a way that minimizes the total intra-

group variance. This approach aims to maximize intra-cluster homogeneity while increasing inter-cluster differences and is preferred because it produces balanced and interpretable clusters, especially in small samples(Ward, 1963).

The squared Euclidean distance was used as the similarity measure. The squared Euclidean distance is defined as follows:

$$d_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^p (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2$$

x_{ik} and x_{jk} represent the k -dimensional scores of firms i and j , respectively; p represents the number of dimensions. This measure quantitatively reveals the level of similarity by calculating the multidimensional distance between firms. As the distance value decreases, the similarity between firms increases(Arnott, 1980; Tekin & Gümüş, 2017).

Agglomeration coefficients and dendrogram structure were considered in determining the number of clusters. The jumps in coefficient values at the merging stages were examined, and the stage where the distance between clusters increased significantly was used as a reference in determining the optimal number of clusters.

Clustering analysis revealed whether sustainability practices within the sector exhibit a homogeneous structure or whether firms are grouped under different compliance profiles. This analysis offers a typological contribution beyond descriptive analyses in terms of classifying sustainability maturity levels.

All statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS software package, and the significance level was accepted as 0.05.

Findings

Empirical findings regarding the TSRS compliance levels of companies operating in the BIST Transportation and Logistics sector and publishing sustainability compliance reports for 2024 are presented. The analyses were conducted within the framework of descriptive statistics, reliability assessment, inter-dimensional correlation analysis, Friedman test, and hierarchical clustering analysis, respectively.

Dimension-based mean and distribution values were examined to reveal the sector's overall sustainability profile. The internal consistency of the created indices was tested to assess the reliability of the measurement structure. In the subsequent stage, the relationships between the dimensions were analyzed, and it was examined whether sustainability practices progressed holistically or piecemeal. Hierarchical cluster analysis was used to assess whether companies were grouped according to their sustainability performance.

This systematic approach enables the analysis of the sector's sustainability maturity level not only at a descriptive level but also from a structural and comparative perspective.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics regarding TSRS dimensions are presented in Table 1. When examining the overall TSRS compliance level of 10 companies that published sustainability compliance reports for 2024 in the BIST Transportation and Logistics sector, it is seen that the TSRS_{Total} average is 0.989. This value indicates that the sustainability compliance level in the sector as a whole is at a medium level when considering the three-tiered rating scale (0–2).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for TSRS Dimensions

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
A Index	10	0.00	2.00	0.903	0.795
B Index	10	0.00	2.00	0.819	0.924
C Index	10	0.44	2.00	1.184	0.616
D Index	10	0.00	2.00	1.050	0.956
TSRS Total	10	0.11	2.00	0.989	0.770

When the averages are examined on a dimension basis, it is seen that the highest level of compliance is observed in the Environmental dimension ($C_{Index} = 1.184$). This dimension is followed by Stakeholder Engagement ($D_{Index} = 1.050$), Governance ($A_{Index} = 0.903$) and social dimension ($B_{Index} = 0.819$), respectively. The fact that the Environmental dimension has a higher average value compared to other dimensions suggests that sector firms have adopted a more systematic and institutionalized reporting approach to environmental sustainability issues. In contrast, the relatively lower average values in the social and governance areas indicate that the level of implementation and reporting in these dimensions remains more limited.

When the distribution measures are examined, it is seen that there is high variation, especially in the social dimension ($SD = 0.924$) and the Stakeholder Engagement dimension ($SD = 0.956$). This situation reveals that there are significant differences among firms in these areas and that the sector does not exhibit a homogeneous structure. In contrast, the lower standard deviation in the environmental dimension (0.616) indicates that firms have a relatively more balanced and similar performance profile in their environmental sustainability practices.

Examining the minimum and maximum values reveals a wide distribution between 0 and 2 across all dimensions. This finding shows that both firms exhibiting low and high levels of compliance coexist within the sector, indicating that the level of sustainability maturity varies among firms.

Reliability Analysis

Internal consistency analyses of the dimensions were evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, and the results are presented in Table 2. The findings show that all the dimensions created have a high level of reliability.

Table 2. Reliability Results (Cronbach's Alpha) for the Dimensions

Dimension	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Governance (A)	12	0.973
Environmental (B)	24	0.998
Social (C)	18	0.954
Stakeholder Engagement (D)	2	0.851

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the governance dimension was calculated as 0.973. The Alpha value for the environmental dimension reached 0.998, indicating extremely strong internal consistency among the items. The Alpha coefficient for the social dimension was determined as 0.954, confirming a high level of reliability. Although the Stakeholder Engagement dimension contains only two items, the Alpha coefficient of 0.851 shows that this dimension also has acceptable and strong internal consistency.

According to generally accepted threshold values in the literature, Alpha coefficients of 0.70 and above are considered acceptable, values of 0.80 and above are considered high, and values of 0.90 and above are considered very high levels of internal consistency. In this context, the fact that all Alpha values obtained in this study are above 0.80 demonstrates that the TSRS dimension indices have an analytically consistent, homogeneous, and reliable measurement structure.

Correlation Analysis

The relationships between the TSRS dimensions were analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, and the results are presented in Table 3. The findings show that there are generally strong and positive relationships between the dimensions.

Table 3. Pearson Correlation Coefficients Between TSRS Dimensions.

	A _{Index}	B _{Index}	C _{Index}	D _{Index}	TSRS _{Total}
A _{Index}	1				
B _{Index}	0.974**	1			
C _{Index}	0.940**	0.879**	1		
D _{Index}	0.772**	0.663*	0.862**	1	
TSRS _{Total}	0.978**	0.933**	0.974**	0.881**	1

Note: N = 10; * p < .05; ** p < .01

Yönetişim (A_{Index}) A very high level of positive and statistically significant correlation was found between the Governance (A_{Index}) and the Social dimension (B_{Index}) ($r = 0.974$; $p < 0.01$). Similarly, a very strong correlation was determined between the Environmental dimension (C_{Index}) and the total index (TSRS_{Total}) at the level of $r = 0.974$; and between the Governance dimension and the total index at the level of $r = 0.978$. These findings show that overall sustainability performance is strongly related to governance and environmental practices in particular.

The Stakeholder Engagement dimension (D_{Index}) shows relatively lower but still significant correlations compared to other dimensions. For example, there is a positive and significant correlation between the Social dimension and D_{Index} at the level of $r = 0.663$ ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that stakeholder engagement practices, while linked to sustainability performance, may exhibit a more independent structural character compared to other dimensions. Overall, the high and positive correlations between the dimensions indicate that sustainability practices are progressing in a holistic rather than fragmented manner within the sector. Firms with a high level of compliance in one dimension are also seen to perform similarly in other dimensions. Furthermore, the high correlation of the TSRS_{Total} index across all sub-dimensions confirms that the composite index is structurally consistent and a highly representative measurement tool.

Friedman Test Results

A Friedman test for related samples was applied to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between the TSRS dimension means. The analysis results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Friedman Test Results for TSRS Dimensions

Test	N	χ^2	df	p
Friedman (Related Samples)	10	5.892	3	0.117

Note: df = degrees of freedom ($k - 1$); $k = 4$ dimensions; significance level = 0.05.

The chi-square value calculated as a result of the Friedman test was found to be $\chi^2(3) = 5.892$, and the corresponding significance level was determined as $p = .117$. Since the obtained p-value is greater than the significance level of .05, it was concluded that there is no statistically significant difference between the dimension means.

In addition, the Kendall's W coefficient calculated for the test is 0.196, which indicates that the difference between the dimensions is at a low-medium level. This result reveals that there is no systematic prioritization towards a particular dimension in sustainability practices.

Although the environmental dimension appears higher in terms of mean in the descriptive statistics, this difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, it can be said that firms in the sector exhibit a relatively balanced distribution in governance, environmental, social and stakeholder engagement dimensions instead of concentrating their sustainability practices on a particular area. This finding is also consistent with the holistic sustainability structure revealed in the correlation analysis.

Clustering Analysis

Hierarchical clustering analysis was applied using the Ward linkage method and squared Euclidean distance to examine the grouping of firms' sustainability performance within the framework of multidimensional profile structures. This method aims to minimize within-cluster variance at each merger step, enabling firms with similar sustainability profiles to be grouped together under the same cluster. The icicle plot presented in Figure 1 illustrates the stepwise merging process among firms and reveals a sharp increase in cluster distance at the final stage of aggregation. This pattern supports the presence of distinct groups of firms within the sector differentiated by their levels of sustainability maturity.

Figure 1. Hierarchical Clustering Dendrogram of Firms Based on TSRS Dimension Indices Using Ward's Method

When the agglomeration coefficients are examined, a significant increase in the coefficient value is observed, especially between stages 8 and 9 (6.651 → 25.013). This sharp jump in the agglomeration coefficient indicates that inter-cluster heterogeneity has significantly increased at this stage and suggests that the optimal number of clusters can be determined at the level of two or three groups. This situation reveals that there are structural divergences in terms of sustainability performance among firms. When the dendrogram structure is also examined, it is seen that rather than a homogeneous distribution within the sector, groups of firms with different sustainability profiles have formed. While some firms are separated into a distinct cluster with a high level of TSRS compliance, some firms are concentrated in clusters exhibiting low or medium levels of sustainability performance. These findings show that the sector does not exhibit a uniform structure in terms of sustainability maturity level, but rather contains clusters of firms with different levels of corporate capacity and strategic approach. Therefore, although sustainability practices show a holistic orientation in the sector, there are significant differences in performance levels among firms.

Discussion

This study examined the TSRS compliance levels of 10 companies in the BIST Transportation and Logistics sector that published sustainability compliance reports for 2024 by indexing them across four dimensions (Governance, Environmental, Social, Stakeholder Engagement). It also analyzed the relationships between dimensions, the differences between dimension averages, and the clustering of company profiles. The entry into force of the TSRS in Turkey as of January 1, 2024, and the regulation of its scope of application by the KGK make this type of

dimensional compliance measurement particularly timely and policy-relevant. (KGK, 2023, 2024c).

The fact that the TSRS_Total average in descriptive statistics is approximately 0.99 indicates that compliance across the sector has not yet fully reached a distribution weighted toward “full compliance,” but that there are signs of institutionalization in certain areas. This view is consistent with findings that sustainability reporting in Turkey has been carried out for many years on a voluntary basis and under different frameworks (GRI, etc.), while the transition to more standardized/regulated structures has accelerated in recent years (Borsa İstanbul A.S., 2016; KPMG, 2024).

Similarly, findings indicating that sustainability reporting in BIST companies is heterogeneous in terms of content and scope, and that reporting is concentrated in certain areas, have also been highlighted in previous studies (Demirel & Erdogan, 2016; Deren Van Het Hof & Hoştut, 2021).

The fact that the Environmental (C_{Index}) dimension has the highest average among the dimensions can be attributed to the nature of transportation/logistics activities, which makes indicators such as energy consumption, emissions, fuel efficiency, waste, and operational environmental impacts more visible and reportable. Studies evaluating sustainability performance in the logistics sector show that environmental indicators often stand out as a “core” area due to their measurability and direct link to operations. Furthermore, sector analyses conducted on BIST Transportation and Storage/Logistics companies in Turkey report that the environmental dimension is a major determinant in measuring sustainability performance and that performance differences between companies are more clearly visible in this area (Jayarathna et al., 2022b; Okur Yazar et al., 2025; Özen Özkan, 2024).

The strong and positive correlations between dimensions in your Pearson correlation results (A–B: 0.974; C–TSRS_{Total}: 0.974; A–TSRS_{Total}: 0.978) indicate that sustainability practices in companies within the sector are not fragmented but rather exhibit a more cohesive structure. Studies examining the restructuring of ESG disclosures in Turkey after 2022 and the relationship between ESG reports/corporate governance mechanisms and ESG scores show that reporting practices have developed within a mutually reinforcing corporate structure (Kartal, Taşkın, et al., 2024; Kartal, Kılıç Depren, et al., 2024).

The excessively high correlations can be explained by “true consistency,” where companies' reporting approaches produce a common effect across dimensions. The trend toward similarity/standardization in the content of sustainability reporting on BIST has also been discussed in earlier content analysis studies (Ferjančić et al., 2024; Uyar, 2017).

The lack of a significant difference between the average scores of the dimensions in the Friedman test ($p=0.117$) can be interpreted at first glance as companies implementing their sustainability practices relatively evenly across the dimensions. It should also be noted that the statistical power of the test may be low due to the limited sample size ($n=10$).

Although the average of the environmental dimension appears higher in descriptive statistics, it can be said that the dimensions remain at a similar level of alignment across the sector. Findings that the balance between dimensions in BIST companies' sustainability reporting varies with company maturity and reporting capacity are consistent with the sustainability reporting literature in the Turkish context (Akin & Güngör Tanç, 2024; Saygili et al., 2023; Serpeninova et al., 2024).

The distinct jump in agglomeration coefficients in your hierarchical clustering analysis using the Ward method indicates that companies cluster into different sustainability profiles based on their TSRS dimension indices. This finding suggests that sustainability maturity is not homogeneous across the sector; while some companies approach an advanced alignment profile, others remain at a lower level of alignment. Studies examining how sustainability

reporting/practices in BIST differ based on company characteristics also support this argument of heterogeneity (Hazır, 2024; Lehenchuk et al., 2024).

Studies examining compliance-based reports such as the “Sustainability Compliance Framework Report” on BIST indicate that reporting is progressing under the “comply or explain” principle and that reporting maturity varies across sectors. Assessments conducted in the banking sector indicate that most institutions publish reports, but the depth of content varies; this is consistent with the general trend and suggests a high adoption rate in the transportation-logistics sector (Akbaş, 2022). Recent studies examining the relationship between compliance performance and non-financial KPI indicate that the indexing and analysis of compliance-based indicators is becoming increasingly common in the literature.(Peker, 2024).

Conclusion

This study systematically and quantitatively assessed the level of compliance of companies in the BIST Transportation and Logistics sector that published sustainability compliance reports for 2024 with the TSRS framework. The indexing model developed under four main dimensions allowed sustainability compliance to be analyzed not only at the level of report publication but also in terms of content depth and scope. In this respect, the study provides a comprehensive measurement framework that makes TSRS applications comparable on a company basis.

The overall picture obtained shows that the sector is in a transition phase in terms of sustainability compliance. It is understood that compliance is widespread but its depth varies between companies; environmental issues in particular have a relatively more institutionalized structure; while there is a more pronounced diversity in social and stakeholder-focused practices. The strong relationships between the dimensions indicate that sustainability is beginning to be addressed in companies not as fragmented areas but rather as an integrated management area. However, the clustering results reveal that there are groups of companies with different levels of sustainability maturity within the sector, indicating that there is no single model of compliance.

These findings indicate that the TSRS has been accepted as a regulatory framework within the sector; however, differences exist among companies in terms of implementation capacity, organizational structure, and strategic priorities. Therefore, it can be said that sustainability compliance is not merely a normative obligation but also a process directly related to corporate strategy and governance capacity.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that TSRS compliance can be analyzed in a measurable and comparable manner at the sector level; it shows that a dimensional and holistic assessment of sustainability performance has the potential to generate meaningful insights for both policymakers and market actors. Future research expanding this framework with designs that include different sectors, multi-year data, and integration with financial performance indicators will contribute to a more in-depth understanding of the economic and managerial outcomes of sustainability compliance.

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